

Large Research Data Storage on Blockchain Technology

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*National Science Data Fabric (NSDF) All-Hands, UCSD
February 29, 2024*

“The National Science Data Fabric is working to democratize data-driven scientific discovery”

“Blockchain-based data solutions are helping to usher in a new era of data democratization”

James Webb Space Telescope

Inter Planetary File System (IPFS)

Interplanetary File System (IPFS)

A **distributed file storage protocol** that allows computers all over the globe to store and serve files as part of a giant network that uses **hashing technology based content addressing** instead of HTTP.

“Protocol Labs and Lockheed Martin demonstrate IPFS data transmission in space, eyeing a future of off-planet networks”

January 16, 2024: “The mission showcased the capabilities of IPFS, a decentralized content distribution system, in enhancing communications across vast distances and bolstering resilience in challenging space environments.”

The largest decentralized
storage network in the world

10 million terabytes

Safeguarding humanity's data

2 million terabytes

Seal Storage

100,000 terabytes

3,000+ nodes that record all network transactions
and verify daily the integrity of the data stored

Seal operates multiple nodes in 2 enterprise data centers

Seal partners with other qualified and selected node operators in data centers around the world to store multiple, decentralized copies.

Total amount of data stored by AWS ?

The LHC produces over 600 million collisions per second,
and ATLAS detectors collect approximately
1 megabyte of data per collision.

10^9 collisions/second x 1 Mbyte/collision

= 1 Petabyte/second

“The amount of data generated will grow by nearly an order of magnitude in the upcoming High Luminosity (HL-LHC) upgrade”

Why Seal?

Blockchain

- Data provenance
- Immutability
- Auditability
- Daily verification

Network Architecture

- Cryptographic security
- Content addressing
- Decentralized
- Programmable

Cost

- 80%+ less than AWS
- Fixed fee structure
- Multiple copies
- No egress fees

Why Seal?

- Leading storage provider on the decentralized network
- Only full stack solution (built in house)
- Enterprise grade (SOC2, HIPAA)
- Working with several research institutions, mass-scale projects
- Selected as World Economic Forum Tech Pioneer

*Neutrino
research*

Berkeley
UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA

 **THE
UNIVERSITY
OF UTAH®**

NSDF

*Blockchain
+ AI/ML
research*

*GEORGETOWN
UNIVERSITY*

NEC

*Responsible
AI*

*Legal Hold
Pilot*

COMCAST

COLUMBIA UNIVERSITY

*Decentralized
Compute on data*

Blockchain Storage & AI/ML

One of the biggest challenges AI/ML faces is _____.

Trust

- Where did the original data come from?
- Who was involved in the data collection?
- Was the process governed by a collection policy?
- Were domain experts consulted through subgroup modeling?
- How were questions of representational bias measured?
- How was the data labeled?
- Who did the data labeling?

**The
Guardian**

'The situation has become appalling': fake scientific papers push research credibility to crisis point

**Last year, 10,000 sham papers had to be retracted by academic
journals, but experts think this is just the tip of the iceberg**

0.998

0.988

0.998

0.988

0.998

0.986

0.997

0.999

0.999

0.991

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deep learning face for Sale,Up To OFF 62%

Datasets are prone to mismanagement

- “Duke MTMC” is a dataset that draws from surveillance footage captured on Duke University’s campus.
 - “LFW” is a dataset that captures photos of faces scraped from various Yahoo News articles.
 - “MS-Celeb-1M” is a dataset released by Microsoft with facial photos of roughly 10,000 different people.
- Problematically, the datasets were combined and used by corporations tied to surveillance operations. Numerous lawsuits followed.

Data Integrity Solutions

- Data provenance
- Chain-of-custody
- Proof of storage
- Proof of replication
- Content identification
- Content verification
- Data rights
- Data sovereignty

An Architecture
for Trust

If you would like to learn more

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In 2023, decentralized VM technology was introduced to the network

2022: Decentralized storage network

2025: Programmable, open data services network

- Distributed computing
- Smart contracts
- Decentralized CDN
- Decentralized applications

“World Economic Forum Names Seal Storage Technology a 2023 Technology Pioneer”

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

How blockchain data storage can protect us from deepfakes

Deepfakes and data integrity are both acute risks in a world driven by artificial intelligence. We can mitigate the challenges of AI by focusing on data.

WORLD
ECONOMIC
FORUM

BLOCKCHAIN

How blockchain can improve data security in healthcare

Technology may be improving healthcare, but it's also driving a rise in data breaches. Blockchain could minimize the risks.

What is a zk-SNARK?

The acronym zk-SNARK stands for Zero-Knowledge Succinct Non-Interactive Argument of Knowledge and refers to a proof construction where one can prove possession of certain information, e.g., a secret key, without revealing that information, and without any interaction between the prover and verifier.

What is a the Filecoin Foundation?

Filecoin Foundation for the Decentralized Web (FFDW) is a 501(c)(3) non-profit whose mission is to ensure the permanent preservation of humanity's most important information by stewarding the development of open-source software and open protocols for decentralized data storage and retrieval networks.

SEAL

CYCLOTRON

